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Research Article

**DESIGN, DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF
EUPHORBIA HIRTA L. HAIR FORMULATION FOR HAIR
GROWTH PROMOTION ON MICE**

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Abstract:-

Hair loss (alopecia) is a common dermatological condition that causes significant psychological stress. This study aimed to design, develop, and evaluate a herbal hair oil formulation using Euphorbia hirta L. (Euphorbiaceae) for hair growth promotion. An ethanolic extract of the whole plant was prepared via maceration and screened for phytochemicals, revealing the presence of flavonoids, tannins, terpenoids, and phenols. A stable herbal oil was formulated by incorporating 2% Euphorbia hirta extract into a coconut oil base using Tween 80 as a surfactant. The hair growth-promoting activity was evaluated in vivo using testosterone-induced alopecia models in Wistar mice. Four groups were studied over 30 days: a control group (sterilized water), a negative control (testosterone-induced), a positive control (0.1 mL of 5% finasteride), and a test group (0.8 mL of 10% Euphorbia hirta oil). Preliminary results suggest that the Euphorbia hirta oil formulation provides a promising natural alternative to synthetic drugs for treating hair growth disorders.

Keywords: Hair Growth Promotion, Alopecia, Herbal Formulation, Phytochemical Screening, Testosterone-Induced Alopecia, Wistar Mice, Flavonoids.

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INTRODUCTION:

The importance of medicinal plants to the mankind is very well proven from ancient time, as early human being solely depended on for their survival on herbs for their food supplement and also for medicines to cure diseases. It is found that majority of the people worldwide depend chiefly on the traditional system of medicines for their health, because of their better adaptability, better compatibility with the human system and fewer or minimum side or untoward effects. The science dealing with herbs and herbal preparation for treating diseases is well known in our country since 3500 BC and traditionally this system of medicine is known as Ayurveda.[1] Various classical Indian texts have described a wide range of medicinal plants and their uses in curing different ailments. The well-established Indian healing processes have been developed from enriched ancient civilizations and scientific heritage (Lele, 1999, Kamboj, 2000) [2,3]. The safety and efficacy of natural herbs could not find any suitable alternative i.e. cannot be replaced by synthetics. According to Alves and Rosa (2007), about 20,000 plant species are used for medicinal purposes [4]. In spite of their crude form, many medicinal plant formulations were outstandingly efficacious against a number of maladies (Dwyer and Rattray, 1993). According to a survey (Cragg et.al., 1997), it has been found that out of 520 new approved drugs during 1983-1994, many were belonging to natural products or derived from natural resources. Furthermore, majority of antimicrobial and antineoplastic drugs were found to be derived from natural products (Harvey, 1999). Herbal cosmetics are the vogue in these days. Herbal cosmetics reflect a sagacious combination of traditional natural drug knowledge and modern processing techniques [5]. Nowadays cosmetology is a well-defined science based on experiences gathered over centuries. The medicinal plant powders and their extracts are formulated to prepare various herbal cosmetics meant for beautification of human beings. There are number of plants and recipes used in modern cosmetics, which take care of skin, check aging and protect early hair fall, graying, wrinkling, and discoloration of the skin. Various modes of herbal utilization are depicted in (Fig. 1.1).

Figure 1: Herbal Utilization

Anatomy and Physiology of the skin

The skin is the outer most covering of every animal body which provides protection to the organism from environment. Without it, survival of mammalian life would not be possible. It works as an excellent indicator of the health and welfare of an animal. It serves many functions such as protection against the harsh environmental conditions, thermoregulation, maintenance of homeostasis, metabolism, excretion and to provide an ornamental accessory to the organism. The skin is the largest organ in humans. It is highly vascular and receives about one-third of blood circulating through the body. The skin is made up of heterogeneous structure, which consists of epithelial cells forming a stratified epidermis containing keratins acting as a protective barrier; mesenchymal cells which forms the underlying dermis along with epithelial cells, facilitating the production of hair follicles and other appendages; hypodermis which regulates energy storage, metabolism; and melanocytes which provide pigmentation to the skin and hair follicles (Fig. 1.2) (Millar 2005). Specialized appendages derived from the ectoderm and/or mesoderm are present within these layers including sensory nerves, sweat glands and hair follicles having important

functions like thermoregulation, homeostasis, defense, sensory functions, communication, reproduction, etc. (Liebich 1993). Also, the skin is highly innervated, and contains large amounts of specialized cells like dendritic Langerhans cells, Merkel mechanoreceptor cells, and mast cells which produce histamine. These varied category of cells undergo extensive interactions, relocation, propagation, and differentiation during embryonic development to attain their present form (Millar 2005).

The location on the body decides the density of structures in the skin, but on average one square centimeter of skin contains about 10 hair follicles and 15 sebaceous glands, 100 sweat glands, half a meter of blood vessels, 2 meters of nerves, with 3,000 sensory cells at the end of nerve fibers, 200 nerve endings for recording pain sensation, 25 pressure receptors for the perception of tactile stimuli, 2 sensory receptors for cold, and 12 sensory receptors for heat (Schaefer 1996)^[6].

Hair, nails, claws, horns, salivary glands, sebaceous glands and mammary glands are the skin appendages, which are transformed from flat epithelia into specialized structures that are either protruding outwards such as the hair, or invaginating inward as for a gland (Liebich 2004). They then diverge into more complex skin appendages e.g. Claws, nails, hair from exvaginating bud and sweat glands, scent glands from the invaginating bud.

Figure 2: T. S of skin showing hair follicle

Hair

Hair is a thin threadlike epidermal structure of about 0.1mm thick, made up of keratin, which is developed from a hair follicle located in the dermis. It is usually produced only by mammals and is characteristic of a particular group of animals. Diversified hair and hair follicles are found all over the body except on the palms, soles, glabrous foreskin and the lip venmillion. Hair consists of hair shaft, which is a permanent, superficial portion from the bulge upward and a lower, inferior portion

which is the root, where the growth cycles anagen, catagen, and telogen are followed in order to produce new hairs^[7].

There are about 10,00,000 - 20,00,000 hair follicle (HF) on the scalp alone. Additional HF is found all over the body, hair is present in every area of the skin except the palms, soles, and lips. The presence of hair in odd place makes a negative effect, whereas hair on the head is a part of overall attraction and beauty of an individual.

Anatomy of Human Hair

Hair Structure

Hair is protienous in nature made up of keratin. On chemical investigation hair found to contains oxygen, iron, nitrogen, hydrogen, carbon, sulfur and phosphorous. The amount of these chemicals varies with the age, sex, type and color of hair of an individual.

Each strand of hair consists of following:

Medulla (The innermost layer)

It is only present in large thick hairs. It consists of several layers of large, loosely packed keratinized cells which may be polygonal or cuboidal in shape. Fat granules, melanin pigment granules, Intercellular and Intracellular air spaces may be present in the medulla.

Cortex (The middle layer)

The cortex gives strength, color, and texture to the hair. The mass of hair shaft is formed by the cortex. The cortical cells are spindle-shaped keratinized cells which are cemented together to form a compact structure. Pigment hair contains longitudinally arranged melanin granules within the cells of the cortex.

Cuticle (The outermost layer)

The cuticle is thin and the layer having no colour which protect the cortex. It is composed of flat, strong, Horney cells. These are interlocked with the cells of innermost hair sheath to support the hair firmly in its follicles. The cuticle also serves to bind the cortical cells together to prevent hair shaft from becoming frayed. Hair with split end is resulted when the cuticle breaks and dislodges. Cuticle is damaged if proper care of hair is not taken and if it is frequently exposed to corrosive chemical agents.

Dermal Papilla

The dermal papilla gives direction and becomes instrumental in generation of embryonic hair follicle. It is made up of very active cells which are involved in induction of hair follicular development from the epidermis. Dermal papilla contains various components such as spindle shaped cells, fibroblast, stroma, collagen bundles, nerve fibers and a single capillary loop. It is contiguous with the dermal sheath of connective tissue that encloses the lower part of hair follicle^[8].

Figure 3: Normal Human Hair Follicle structure

Hair growth & Distribution (Waldman & Brown 1974)

- The earliest sign of hair growth (HG) can be observed in the fetus as early as the end of the 2nd month of fetus life in the region of eyebrows, the upper lips, and the chin. Follicles are formed all over the scalp and face during the 4th and 6th month subsequently the remaining body surface except the palm and soles.
- The first hair is formed by the follicle in utero are the lanugo type which is fine and soft, unmedullated and often has no pigment.
- As the fetus grows the lanugo hairs are shed during the 7th and 8th month of its life and are being replaced by vellus hair in all area except the scalp; where a coarse hair resembling terminal hair of the adult are produced.
- Vellus hairs are also fine and soft and are generally not pigmented and rarely attain a length of 1-2 cm. The vellus hair generally shed over the first 4 months of life and is

replaced by the most vellus hair or intermediate hairs in most area.

- At puberty the vellus hair of the pubic region then the auxiliary and finally the remainder of the body surface being replaced by the terminal hair which are longer and coarser than vellus hair to possess a medulla or pigmentation.
- On face region, the hair transition occurs from vellus to terminal in orderly sequences from the outer portion of the upper lips to the chin and then to the cheeks and then to the remainder of the bearded area. Distribution of hairs in male and female on their face is during the adolescences, the terminal hairs at formal hairline undergo replacement from vellus hairs, in the male, it is 100% and, in the female, it is 80%^[10].

Types of Hair

Lanugo Type

After birth the hair present on the scalp, initially known as “lanugo” hair, fall in a more or less harmonized manner within first six months of birth. The surface of this hair is delicate with close to indiscriminate scales. These are replaced later on by vellus and terminal hair.

Vellus Type

They are the fine, excellent, soft and unmedullated hair distributed uniformly over the physique of body with a length of 2.0 cm in size.

Terminal Type

These hairs are bigger hair with less thickness and having length more than 1.0 cm. They contain more pigment and are originated from deep dermis layer of the skin. They are found on the scalp, eyebrows, and eyelashes and to a very less extent on the limbs of both sexes. Puberty is accompanied by growth of pubic and axillary hair development on the face, chest, palms and legs^[11].

Number of Hairs (Giacometti 1965)

It is estimated that each adult individual has an average number of 5 million HF found at different densities. With advancement of age-progressive loss of HF is observed as follows:

At the age of 20-30 the average HF present are 615/cm².

At the age of 30-50 the average HF present are 485/cm².

At the age of 80-90 the average HF present are $430/\text{cm}^2$ ^[13].

Hair Growth

The hair grows at different rate which is commonly observed at different parts of the human body. The rate of growth also varies between male and female body.

The rate of hair growth at different parts of the body is observed as follows (Saitoh *et.al.*, 1969).

Growth rate:

0.44mm/day on Scalp

0.44mm/day on Chest

0.39mm/day on temples

0.27mm/day on beard

Average hair growth is affected slightly by the age of human being, but overall average hair growth rate per day is 0.37mm (Pelfini *et.al.*, 1969)^[14].

Chemistry of Hair

Human hair is composed of almost entirely of keratin a protein that has outstanding properties as below:

It is totally insoluble in acids, alkalies, and is insoluble in solvents which can dissolve any other proteins. It is resistant to enzymatic digestions. These outstanding properties of keratin are attributed to the presence of a comparatively high percentage of cysteine, an amino acid. Keratin fibers are composed of long polypeptides chains, which are connected laterally by various linkages. (Sharma, 1998)

Hair Pigmentation

The color of hair is resulted due to formation of pigments into the newly formed cells. The pigment is manufactured with the melanocytes and transforms the cells of both the cortex and medulla. (Fitzatric *et al.*, 1958)

The shade or color of human hair depends on the pigment present. In human two type of pigments is present which is responsible for the shade or color of an individual. The pigment presents are: Eumelanin which gives black or brown color to hair

and the other one is Phaeomelanin, which gives yellow or reddish colour to the hairs. Phaeomelanin contains more iron in it. Eumelanin is produced by the enzymatic oxidation of tyrosine and it is insoluble in any solvent while Phaeomelanin is produced by tyrosinase but it seems that the presence of an O-amino-phenol derived from tryptophan is also required. (Fitzatric *et.al.*, 1958)

Due to the change in metabolism, pigment melanin is not formed and therefore not carried with the cells and pushed up and hence hair becomes gray. The premature graying may occur due to several reasons like hyperthyroidism or pernicious anemia. (Rook *et.al.*, 1979). There is no known medical treatment by which tyrosinase activity of melanocytes and transfer of pigment can be restored as hair becomes gray in the aging scalp^[15].

Hair Follicle

- Hair is originated from the small pockets present in the dermis layer of skin known as follicle. It is widely distributed over the entire scalp except few places and is found in groups. The wall of the follicle forms the (outer root sheath) ORS and the lower part widen out or bulges out to form the hair bulb.
- This hair follicle contains the germinal matrix which is mainly responsible for the hair growth and its development. Inside the hair follicle the hair is surrounded by three layers known as Henle's (He), Huxley's (Hx) and Cuticle. The He is one cell thick while Hx is 3 to 4 cell thick and the cuticle covers both the inner root sheath and the outer root sheath.
- The hair follicle is mainly responsible for the formation of a hair fiber. It is a complex organ made up of different types of epithelial and dermal tissues. The 3D appearance of the follicle determines the final shape of the fiber: if it is straight (Mongolians), slightly bent (Caucasians) or helical form (Africans).

Embryology of Hair Follicle

Hair follicle development in the embryo begins following the initial stages of epidermal differentiation (Blanpain and Fuchs, 2009; Schmidt-Ullrich and Paus, 2005). The inductive interactions of dermal and epidermal tissues are therefore likely to play an important role in regulating hair follicle growth not only during embryogenesis but also in the mature cycling follicle.

Following formation of an undifferentiated epidermal layer, hair follicle induction begins with an exchange of signals both within and between epidermal keratinocytes and the underlying dermal fibroblasts of mesenchymal origin. The formation of a “hair placode” characterizes the initial stages of hair follicle development, appearing as small invaginations of the epidermis^[17].

Hair Follicle Development

Normally there are different stages in hair follicle development which are as follows: (Ronald Shapiro, 2004)

Pre Germ Stage

The grouping of nuclei in the epidermal basal layer is the first sign of follicular development. At this stage the mesenchymal cells are aggregated in the dermis and the basal layer of epidermis starts to become thick.

Figure 4: Pre-Germ Stage

Hair Germ Stage

In this stage, the basal cells after becoming tall and the shape begins to (bulge) and develop downwards into the corium as “hair germ”. Further, the mesenchymal cells and the fibroblasts increase in quantity to make the substructure of the dermal papilla, which is present below the hair germ.

Figure 5: Hair Germ Stage

Hair Peg Stage

The hair germ grows obliquely into the mesenchyme as an excellent column or “Hair Peg” of cells belongs to epithelium, located above the dermal papilla.

Figure 6: Hair Peg Stage

Bulbous Peg-Stage

The column proceeds to elongate and three swellings are observed. The underneath is the substructure of the sweat gland and above to it is the substructure of tubular epitrichial gland. The advancing base of the column takes the shape of a bulb and encloses part of under layer. The cells of the matrix area surrounding the dermal papilla now begin to divide the activity and the first hair, capped by keratinizing cells of the IRS starts begins to force it away outwards. Above it, central cells of the follicular peg appear to retrogress and the rising hair appears to push out the plug to produce a hair canal. The primary follicle develops at an interval of between 274 & 350 μm over the dermis surface. It is traditionally approved that new follicle cannot improve in grown up epidermis^[18].

Figure 7: Bulbous Peg Stage

The First Primordial Hair

During this period the cells at dermal papilla grow to form a mold and the hair shaft is developed. Finally, the hair canal is produced due to modification of cells located in the follicular peg and pushing of plug by the emerging hair.

Figure 8: Primordial Hair Stage

Hair Growth Cycle

The hair follicle growth cycle shows the diversified morphological feature of the shaft and the histological feature of follicle. All body hairs undergo this cycle, though there is difference in duration of cycle of the individual phases as well as the length of the individual hair shafts. Every hair follicle has its characteristic pattern. That's why they are nonparallel with the neighboring follicle.

It is not clear as to how the hair cycle spreads in waves, though research suggests

that these growth waves are controlled by intrinsic factors of the hair follicle group in a "reaction-diffusion" system. Nearby follicles and systemic stimuli have the influence in the intrinsic rhythm (Jhonson 1965). Hence the cycle is essentially autonomous and has an inherent pattern where in it is influenced by environmental systemic and local factors (Chase 1965). Follicular morphogenesis and the first postnatal catagen, telogen, and anagen development of the hair follicle follow a precise time-scale (Chase 1951). However, the genetic background, the sex, environmental factors and nutritional factors also play an important role [19].

Anagen

This is the active growth phase of the hair cycle where metabolically active and dividing cells above and around the dermal papilla of the follicle grow upward to form the hair shaft. The proliferation rate is more and is observed in all hair follicle cells and epithelial compartments with matrix cells exhibiting the highest intensity. The duration of anagen is predetermined genetically and varies with the size and location of the hair follicle. It may last several years or may persist only for few weeks.

Catagen

Catagen is of short duration which is initiated at late anagen and concluded at early telogen. It is

characterized by a fundamental restructuring of the extracellular matrix. This involves involution of the hair follicle and cessation of protein and pigment production. In this stage onset of the apoptosis is predetermined and finely designed, resulting in degeneration of two thirds of the hair follicle. The club hair is formed when the part of the hair follicle in contact with the lower portion of the hair becomes attached to the hair shaft. Catagen is the first module of the initial hair cycle occurring after morphogenesis.

Telogen

In this stage the hair follicle degenerate to about half of its previous size and does not extend beyond the upper dermis. The dermal papilla is no longer enveloped by surrounding epithelial cells and sits as a small band of cells in close association with the epithelial cell. However, keratin synthesis does continue in the epithelial sac to which the telogen hair fiber anchors. In telogen follicles, the volume of the dermal papilla extracellular matrix is much reduced and dermal papilla cells have few cytoplasm and are relatively quiescent. The telogen hair shaft can be retained for months in this epithelial sac.

Exogen

Exogen is a specific process in hair follicle cycling (Stenn 2005). The exogen root is made up of very few cells and these cells are separated at their outer edge by intercellular cleavage. The morphology of the hair root suggests that the exogen process involves a proteolytic event that occurs between the moving cells of the telogen shaft base. A possible role of desmoglein and proteolytic events are suggested (Koch 1998).

Kenogen

This is the interval phase of the hair follicle cycle in which the hair follicle remains empty after shedding of the hair fiber and the telogen hair has been extruded and before a new anagen hair emerges.

Figure 9: Hair growth cycle: Anagen, Catagen, and Telogen.

Figure 10: Hair growth cycle: Anagen, Catagen, and Telogen

Hair Loss / Hair Disease

Loss of hair is associated with problems in the skin. This has derived researchers to explore promising medicinal plants possessing better hair growth enhancing property (Arakawa *et.al.*, 1962, Adhirajan *et.al.*, 2003). Hair loss, dandruff, hirsutism, alopecia areata are the common patient complaints, which are the sources of significant psychological and physical stress (Han A.2006). A number of natural hair care products in form of herbal formulations are available in the market, which are used against hair loss as well as other hair related diseases (Olsen 1993). Hair loss is also resulted from various other factors such as aging, genetic pre-disposition, thyroid imbalance, malnutrition or imbalance diet, chronic illness, hormonal effects of contraceptive pills, pregnancy, or menopause, certain medications and radiation therapy /chemotherapy used for treating cancer, etc. The androgenetic alopecia (AGA) also known as male pattern hair loss (MPLS), female pattern hair loss (FPLS) and alopecia areata (AA) are the most common forms of non-scarring hair loss. People are nowadays spending a good amount towards hair related diseases. Ayurveda has also classified hair diseases into three types:

1. **Khalitya** means loss of hairs.
2. **Palitya** means premature hair graying.
3. **Indralupta** means alopecia areata (AA), totalis, universalis^[20].

Figure 11: Other Causes of Hair Loss

Androgenetic Alopecia and Female Pattern Hair Loss

Androgenetic alopecia is the most common form of hair loss affecting male/female which attributes to over 95% of hair loss reported worldwide. It is the most common type of alopecia, affecting about 50% of Caucasian males and females beyond age 40 years (Rhodes *et.al.*,1998, Hamilton JB 1951). The severity of the disease varies from merely accentuated recession of the frontal hairline to loss of all hair except along the temporal and occipital margins. It is a progressive disease resulting in decrease in density of terminal hair and a resulting increase in vellus hairs.

Although etiology of the disease is still unclear, but it is observed that cell culture work by Hibberts and co-workers (Hibberts *et.al.*, 1998) proposes the increased perception of hair follicles to dihydro testosterone leads to androgenetic alopecia especially during post puberty period. Sawaya and Price (Sawaya *et.al.*,1997) demonstrated that the concentration of androgen receptor protein within the dermal papilla fibroblasts and outer root sheath are 30% greater in the balding frontal follicles as compared to the non-balding frontal hair follicles. Increased androgen binding at these receptor sites resulted in distinct effects on the physiology of hair follicles.

1.14.2 Alopecia areata

Alopecia areata is an organ-specific autoimmune disorder characterized by non-scarring hair loss that may occur patchy or generalized (Barahmani *et.al.*, 2009, Chu *et.al.*, 2011). It has been observed

occurring in association with several autoimmune diseases including thyroid and vitiligo and nail abnormalities (Muller SA 1963, Hordinsky M., 2001). Alopecia areata is commonly seen throughout the world affecting both young and old age group individuals (Finner AM., 2011). It is estimated that 0.2% to 2% of the US population alone is affected by this disease and the individual lifetime risk is estimated to be approximately 1.7% (Safavi K 1992, Safavi *et.al.*, 1995). About 25% of patients have a genetic history of the disorder, however, various report shows familial incidences range from 3 - 42% (Mc Donagh *et.al.*, 1996). Usually, half of patients affected with alopecia areata recover their hair loss within a year and some may face total loss of scalp hair (alopecia totalis) or loss of the entire scalp and body hair (alopecia universalis). In spite of high occurrence of Alopecia areata, still adequate therapies are not available to tackle this disease, only very few therapies are available that have been tested using placebo (Delamere *et.al.*, 2008).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

In vivo assay of plant extract for hair growth activity

Experimental Animals:

Wistar mice of either sex (20-30g) or 8–12-week age would be used for study. The animals were housed for 7 days in the animal house of Narasaraopeta Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Narasaraopeta on a 12 light/dark cycle under controlled temperature ($22^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$) and humidity ($50 \pm 10\%$). Experiments are performed in accordance with the committee for the purpose of control and supervision of experimental animals CPCSEA) guidelines after approval of the experimental protocols by the institutional animal ethics committee (IAEC).^[21]

Figure 12: - Weighing and grouping of Animals

Protocol of treatment:

The mice were randomly allocated into four groups (n = 6). To create a baseline for comparison and isolate the treatment effects,

1. **control group (Group 1)** was given sterilized water.
2. **Group 2 (Testosterone-induced group):** Received a daily subcutaneous dose of 5% testosterone solution (100 μ L) for 30 days, without any further treatment.
3. **Group 3 (Finasteride-treated group):** Received a daily topical dosage of 0.1 mL of 5% finasteride solution one hour after testosterone treatment for 30 days.
4. **Group 4 (*Euphorbia hirta* Oil - treated group):** Received a daily topical application of 0.8 mL of 10% *Euphorbia hirta* Oil one-hour post-testosterone application for 30 days.

All interventions were administered to the depilated dorsal epidermis of the mice.

Hair population Evaluation (Quantitative):

All mice were anesthetized with intra peritoneal (i.p) injection of ketamine (100mg/kg) and xylazine (10mg/kg) after 30 days of experiment (without causing distress or death). The dorsal areas with 2cm in width and 4cm in length of the mice were clipped with clippers.^[22]

Hair density Evaluation

In these evaluation parameter mice of group subjected to evaluated to hair density by square area method. Dorsal areas of mice firstly made 1 mm² of area and count the hair in particular area and

measure and recorded the density of hair. Follicular density (number of hair Follicles per mm) and anagen/telogen ratio was calculated.

Figure 13: - Hair growth in different treatment groups

Measurement of hair length:

Model for the evaluation of hair growth measurement was performed. Hair was plucked randomly using sterile forceps from the depilated area on 30th day of treatment and the hair length was measured with the help of scale and the results were calculated as mean length \pm SEM of 25 hairs.^[21]

Figure: 14- Measurement of Hair length

RESULTS & DISCUSSION:**Quantitative Results**

Changes in Hair Follicle Density: Increased density suggests successful intervention or a less severe progression of alopecia. Decreased density indicates hair follicle loss or damage, which is common in hormone-induced alopecia.

Table-1:- Follicular density and anagen/telogen ratio in sections of skin of different groups of animals.

S. No.	Groups	Follicular density (no./mm)	Anagen/telogen ratio
		Mean \pm SE	
1.	control group (Group 1)	2.167 \pm 0.166	1.54:1
2.	Group 2 (Testosterone-induced group)	1.167 \pm 0.3073	0.5:1
3.	Group 3 (testosterone+Finasteride-treated group):	2.833 \pm 0.1667	1.60:1
4.	Group 4 (testosterone+Euphorbia hirta Oil -treated group)	2.667 \pm 0.2108	1.23:1

Figure 15: - Follicular Density (nn/mm)

Figure 16: - Anagen/Telogen ratio

Measurement of hair length:

Model for the evaluation of hair growth measurement was performed. Hair was plucked randomly using sterile forceps from the depilated area on 30th day of treatment and the hair length was measured with the help of scale and the results were calculated as mean length \pm SEM of 25 hairs.

Increased Growth Rate: Could reflect effective treatment or hormonal modulation.

Decreased Growth Rate: May signify impaired hair growth due to hormonal imbalance.

Table - 2: - Effect of *Euphorbia hirta* Oil on hair growth

S. No.	Groups	Length of animal's hair
		After 30 days (in mm) Mean \pm SEM
1.	control group (Group 1)	11.263 \pm 0.57
2.	Group 2 (Testosterone-induced group)	5.551 \pm 0.10
3.	Group 3 (testosterone+Finasteride-treated group):	11.235 \pm 0.21
4.	Group 4 (testosterone+ <i>Euphorbia hirta</i> Oil -treated group)	11.216 \pm 0.26

Figure 24: - Increased and decreased growth rates of four groups

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:**Summary**

- Study aimed to evaluate *Euphorbia hirta* for hair growth promotion and contains phytochemicals like flavonoids, tannins, phenols
- Extract prepared by ethanolic maceration and herbal oil formulated using coconut oil and Tween 80
- Tested on Wistar mice (4 groups) and parameters evaluated: hair length & follicular density
- *Euphorbia hirta* group showed increased hair growth and results were comparable to finasteride

Conclusion

- *Euphorbia hirta* hair oil showed significant hair growth activity by increasing hair length and follicular density in mice.
- The formulation improved the anagen phase and reversed testosterone-induced hair loss, with results comparable to standard treatment (finasteride).
- The presence of phytochemicals supports its effectiveness, suggesting it as a safe and promising herbal alternative for hair loss

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